

FAIR Workflows to establish IGSN for Samples in the Helmholtz Association

D3 - Assisting and Assessing User application
of the FAIR SAMPLES Template (AWI)

Authors

Mareike Wieczorek (AWI)

Birgit Heim (AWI)

Alexander Brauser (GFZ)

Kirsten Elger (GFZ)

Linda Baldewein (Hereon)

Publication Date: November 30th, 2022

References

Deliverable Report and Questionnaire:

Wieczorek; M.; Heim, B.; Brauser, A.; Elger, K.; Baldewein, L. (2022) FAIR WISH D3 - Assisting and Assessing User application of the FAIR SAMPLES Template. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377904>

Video Tutorial for the FAIR SAMPLES Template:

Wieczorek, M., Brauser, A., Heim, B., Baldewein, L., & Elger, K. (2022). Video Tutorial for the FAIR SAMPLES Template. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7381390>

Video Tutorial on Youtube: <https://youtu.be/SflbTUtknNo>

Table of contents

1. Introduction	3
1.1 Purpose of this document	3
2. FAIR WISH Video Tutorial	3
3. FAIR WISH Usability questionnaire	4
4. FAIR WISH Survey	4
5. Discussion	5
6. References	5
7. Appendix	6
7.1. List of acronyms	6

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

This document describes the deliverable D3 “*Assisting and Assessing User application of the FAIR SAMPLES Template*” of the project **FAIR Workflows** to establish IGSN for **Samples** in the **Helmholtz Association (FAIR WISH)** funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC). Deliverable D3 is part of work package 3 “*Domain-specific metadata for terrestrial and aquatic Geo-Bio samples (vegetation, sediment, water, rocks)*”.

In D2 we provided an exemplary standardised, flexible and customisable metadata template for Geo-Bio samples (in short ‘FAIR SAMPLES Template’) for *batch uploading sample-metadata to the IGSN server*.

D3 includes a video tutorial with complementary visual and audio content on how to use the ‘FAIR SAMPLES Template’. D3 also contains a Usability questionnaire for receiving feedback on the application of the template. The feedback based on these Usability questionnaires and more future activities such as one-to-one interviews will form the main feedback for evaluating the usability of the FAIR SAMPLES Template and improve its applicability.

2. FAIR WISH Video Tutorial

The video tutorial with audio contains FAIR WISH expert demonstrations and explanations. The ultimate goal of the video tutorial is to instruct users how to use the FAIR SAMPLES Template. The video begins with an introduction to the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC), the FAIR WISH project, the International Generic Sample Number (IGSN) and the overall motivation for making samples uniquely identifiable and citable by IGSN assignment. The content then changes to the main part of the tutorial, focussing on the FAIR SAMPLES “Excel” Template, its content and functionalities. In this part, the speaker guides the audience on how to use the template with the different categories of metadata for a sample. The video tutorial applies visual and audio content together as complementary streams of information to facilitate the understanding of the application of the template. According to the recommendations in Brame (2016) the video tutorial contains visual signalling to enhance important information, mostly in the form of highlighting important elements by colour or contrast and cut-out visualisation techniques. The video tutorial uses conversational language and the tutor’s speaking rate is relatively quickly to not lose the attention of the audience throughout the tutorial. We explicitly did not integrate a “talking head” video of the speaker

because watching the speaker would not have provided additional or helpful information and would require too much attention from the attendant of the video tutorial. To produce the tutorial, OBS Studio 27.2 was used for screen recording and Blender 2.9 for video editing.

3. FAIR WISH Usability questionnaire

The aim of the Usability questionnaire is to gather reliable feedback on the user's experience from a representative number of users in the Earth and Environmental science domain that use samples in their research. Usability questionnaires are a commonly used approach for user-driven assessment of usability of tools (e.g., Laugwitz et al. 2008). For that purpose, the Usability questionnaire focuses on how the respondents got along with the FAIR SAMPLES Template. The questionnaire starts with more general questions. Did the respondents know how to use it? Were they able to describe their samples in a sufficient way and find all necessary variables? After the more general questions, the questionnaire continues with specific questions, e.g. the respondents' experience with the linked supplied controlled vocabularies for some of the metadata fields of the template. The questionnaire contains two types of response formats, one having a controlled list of possible answers and one with free text, so that especially critical comments can - and should - be given as detailed as wanted.

The link to the FAIR WISH questionnaire will be sent out personally.

4. FAIR WISH Survey

We will set out a detailed survey to the group of our users of the FAIR SAMPLES Template: We will i) compile the report on the feedback results from the Usability questionnaires and ii) plan to conduct one-on-one interviews successively after receiving metadata from the FAIR SAMPLES Templates. Already, upon approaching possible users, we asked them for their willingness to give us detailed feedback on their user experience. A comprehensive summary on the quantitative and qualitative assessment of the Usability questionnaire (e.g. Schrepp et al. 2017 on Usability Questionnaires) and the one-on-one interviews will be presented together with the final harmonised metadata template as FAIR WISH D4.

5. Discussion

The FAIR SAMPLES Template to fill with sample description metadata is designed to be user-friendly and customisable, i.e. in addition to the mandatory fields, users can select only applicable metadata fields and don't need to use the full metadata schema. Nevertheless, the application of the template requires some explanation and time to fill it with the sample metadata. In D3 we provide a range of tools for assisting and assessing user application of the FAIR SAMPLES metadata templates:

- i) The video tutorial assists the user in the application of the template.
- ii) The Usability questionnaire and interviews provide the users' feedback and potential information on usability problems together with good insights into the needs of the different users in the Earth and Environment sciences, as it gives them sufficient time to engage with the template and feedback in depth.

Our ultimate goal is to use the D3 components to optimise the template towards a flexible template for sample metadata for a wide range of user communities in the Earth and Environment sciences and their samples.

6. References

- Brame, C. J. (2016). Effective Educational Videos: Principles and Guidelines for Maximizing Student Learning from Video Content. In K. E. Perez (Ed.), *CBE—Life Sciences Education* (Vol. 15, Issue 4, p. es6). American Society for Cell Biology (ASCB). <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.16-03-0125>
- Laugwitz, B., Held, T., & Schrepp, M. (2008). Construction and Evaluation of a User Experience Questionnaire. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science* (pp. 63–76). Springer Berlin Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-89350-9_6
- Schrepp, M., Hinderks, A., & Thomaschewski, J. (2017). Construction of a Benchmark for the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ). In *International Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Artificial Intelligence* (Vol. 4, Issue 4, p. 40). Universidad Internacional de La Rioja. <https://doi.org/10.9781/ijimai.2017.445>

7. Appendix

7.1. List of acronyms

AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research
FAIR	Guiding Principles for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable research data (Wilkinson et al., 2015)
FAIR WISH	FAIR Workflows to establish IGSN for Samples in the Helmholtz Association
GFZ	German Research Centre for Geosciences
HMC	Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration
IGSN	International Generic Sample Number